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APPRAISAL OF THE ACCEPTABILITY OF FORENSIC EVIDENCE AS MEANS OF PROOF UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

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Abstract

Islamic Law, as an element of universal religion, Islam, with distinct and perfect system that govern human being in relation to his Creator and his fellow human beings has established golden principles of evidence. The essence of evidence is to assist parties establish their case and the judge to reach a fair decision based on evidence. Forensic findings and other computer based analysis have tremendous influence in the contemporary global affairs be it commercial, social political etc. Forensic evidence related cases were recorded in many suits in various nations. Neither the Glorious Quran nor the Prophetic traditions bound the Muslim to adhere to a particular mode of proving or disproving fact(s). It is therefore, certain that facts remain proven under Islamic Law as it is accordance with the acceptable conventional way. This study appraised the use of Forensic Evidence as means of proof under Islamic law, and the researcher adopted the doctrinal method where reliable texts (nusus) from the Quran, Sunnah and the opinion of Muslim jurists were utilized. It findings revealed that, once forensic evidence is authentic and reliable, Shariah Courts may admit same in the determination of civil or criminal suit. The paper recommended among other things that, scholars of Islamic law as well as Shariah courts judges should be literate in Information and Communication Technology for better application of Islamic Law of evidence in cases related to forensic evidence.

Key words: Forensic, Evidence, Acceptability, Facts.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This paper focuses on forensic evidence, its meaning, nature, functions and admissibility. More so, it discusses the admissibility of forensic evidence under Islamic law.

Modern means of proof in the form of forensic evidence has become an integral part of the law of evidence in the western legal system as well as Islamic legal system. More so, evidence to match the soles of shoes found at the crime scene with that of an accused constitutes an evidence of his conviction with the crime after through and diligence investigation, Photography may also be admitted as credible evidence in both criminal and civil cases.¹ The paper is also aimed to look at the admissibility or other wise of forensic evidence. And provide suitable recommendations. The methodology adopted in writing this article is doctrinal method.

Forensic evidence can be accepted and admitted as evidence under Islamic law provided its authenticity and genuinity is established, this is because the ultimate aim of Shariah is to ensure justice is attained, the process of attaining may vary depending on the circumstance of each case.

2.0 DEFINITION, NATURE AND FUNCTION OF FORENSIC EVIDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

Forensic evidence signifies an expert's scientific opinion, either about the evidential worth, or other matters in connection to a case which is likely to be outside the experience or knowledge of the Judge or Jury (including the prosecution or lawyers).² It is also defined as evidence obtained by scientific methods and used in court.³

Forensic evidence can also be referred to as evidence based on science and law or evidence obtained by the use of science.⁴ Forensic evidence is any evidence relating to or denoting other application of scientific methods and techniques to the investigation of crime.⁵ It also means any evidence that can be used to link crimes that are thought to be related to one another⁶. Accordingly, Forensic evidence is defined as application of

¹[http://: www.forensicscience. OCT. \(2000\). communications.htm](http://www.forensicscience.OCT.(2000).communications.htm) accessed 22/9/15

²<http://www.contactpakistan.com/communitylibrary/general/article0504.htm> accessed 22/9/15

³[http://: www.forensic.science. Org](http://www.forensic.science.Org) visited on 18/3/2019

⁴ Ibid.

⁵[https://: www.the balance careers.com](https://www.thebalancecareers.com) accessed 18/3/2019

⁶ Ibid.

investigation and analysis techniques to gather and preserve from a particular computing device in a way that is suitable for presentation in a court.⁷

Forensic evidence today has become a vital part of civil and criminal investigation in the globe. The main thrust of forensic evidence is to scientifically prove or disprove facts which are outside the knowledge of a lay witness.⁸ For instance, in a civil suit for damages, the question of causation cannot be affirmatively disposed of, unless scientific opinion is given by relevant expertise. Likewise, in a case of murder, the prosecution supports its case with a number of scientific evidence in the form of forensic opinions, which are far beyond the experience of the ordinary examiners of facts, and lawyers for that matter.⁹

Forensic evidence, beside its use to determine the liability or otherwise of the defendant, has also been assigned other robust roles in the administration of justice. For instance, to determine the personality type of the accused so as to consider his plea for mitigation of the sentence against him. The opinion of a forensic psychologist (psychiatrist) should be sought,¹⁰ or to examine his mental make up to prove the truth of his defense of provocation. Forensic anthropology is utilized to compare the feet pattern of the defendant's footprints with that of his group among the population, this was resorted to as a defense in the case of *People V Pollute*¹¹ who was indicted on the basis of an analysis connecting him to crime on the basis of matching the sole of his shoes with the one found at a crime scene.

Opinion of other relevant experts in forensic analysis are required to ascertain the consistency of the traces of evidence found on the person charged,¹² consequently, forensic evidence by its nature embraces a multitude of scientific opinions that assist in a number of ways to implement justice.

Forensic evidence emanating from different disciplines is essential in proving a wide range of issues and facts, contested before the court. A cursory look at what might be during a trial and prosecution before a court, or arbitration as the case may be. It is clear

⁷[https://: www. Forensic Wikipedia.org](https://www.ForensicWikipedia.org) accessed 18/3/2009

⁸Sayeed Shah, *Journal of Islamic Studies*, vol. 4 -6 no. 21 (summer 2007)

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Sikanadar, S, 'Modern Means of Proof, Legal Basis for its Accommodation in Islam, (2006) Vol. 20, No. 4" *Arab Law Quarterly Journal* , p .335.

¹¹ California. Court of. Appeal .(law) 1981

¹² Sikanadar, S, op cit, p. 336

that forensic experts from a variety of disciplines play significant role in judicial proceedings. Today in an action for breach of e-commerce transaction, the need for computer experts and accountants is paramount. In a suit for environmental pollution caused by a particular industry, expert's opinion from different forensic disciplines will be of paramount importance. Criminal cases in particular, require more extensive use of scientific opinions originating from a variety of disciplines such as, medicine, psychology, ballistic, anthropology, information technology, etc. as in the case of *Knox V State of Ind.*¹³The key evidence in a suit for sexual harassment, was the e-mail messages that the defendant sent to the complainant¹⁴

3.0 EXAMPLES OF FORENSIC EVIDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

The following are some of the examples of forensic evidence which are so common and can easily be perceived by majority of Muslims regardless of his or her level of literacy or otherwise.

3.1 POST MORTEM

Post mortem is an examination of the dead body of the victim of a murder case. It is a sort of circumstantial evidence as it is used to establish the identity of an unknown person or to ascertain the cause of death.¹⁵

Under Islamic law human being should be accorded some respect dead or alive. That is why post mortem is not lawful except on grounds of necessity. Sometimes death may occur and the reason and circumstances of the death may be unknown.¹⁶ Therefore, circumstances may necessitate the post mortem to examine the corpse and find out the cause of death.¹⁷

Council of *Ulamas* (scholars) of Saudi Arabia made some rulings on the 20 *Shaaban* 1396 A.H. (12th December 1975) on the legality of post mortem in three situations:¹⁸

Firstly, for the purpose of ascertaining the person responsible for the death of another.

¹³ 13 I S C 281

¹⁴ Cited in Allan M. Ghatan, "Admissibility of Electronic Evidence," *Canada, Carswell, 1999 Journal of Administration of Criminal Law*, p. 2.

¹⁵ Anwarullah, op cit, p. 14

¹⁶ Alzaharaniy, op cit p. 12

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Anwarullah, op cit. p. 14

Secondly, for the purpose of ascertaining the nature of the disease that cause the death in order to address its future occurrence.

Thirdly, for the purpose of teaching and learning for the benefit of medical students.

3.2 DETERMINATION OF PATERNITY

However, it is observed that in a decided case¹⁹ Islamic jurist are not unanimous in their view as to the application of expert opinion on some matters. Although Imam Malik School of Islamic jurisprudence recognizes and relies on the evidence of experts on some matters whenever necessary, medical report in determining paternity is considered unreliable. *Tabsiratul Hukkam* VOL.11 pg 100 corroborates the above statement, which states thus:

“The popular view is that the opinion of an expert cannot be relied upon to ascertain paternity in relation to children of free woman but (same can be relied upon) to establish paternity in case of children of slave woman whose two masters had inter course with her in the period of her purity.”²⁰

The contents of the above passages are very clear in the instant case, as it is not shown that the respondent was a slave. There was therefore no need for any medical examination to establish paternity.

4.0 ADMISSIBILITY OF FORENSIC EVIDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

Forensic evidence in the present day being a type of expert opinion (*ra'ayal-khabir*), draws support for its legitimacy and use under Islamic law from the prophetic traditions (*sunnah*) the consensus of companions' (*Ijama of Sahabah*), and interpretations of Jurists (*Ijtihad*). The basic law pertaining embracing of any useful means of proof, including forensic evidence is founded in a *hadith* in which the Prophet (SAW) as part of his universal inauguration of Islamic judicial proceeding declared that human technical knowledge and expertise, and not the revelation alone, constitute the foundation of evidence and proof. It is clear from his famous dictum when he was reported to have said:

“Since I am only a human, like all of you, I might, when litigants come before me to decide between them, rule in favor of more eloquent of them, if I thereby transfer to him what is

¹⁹ Rabiul V Amadu (2013) 1 SQLR Pt 1.

²⁰ Ibid.

rightfully his brother's, I warn him to take not that which is not his, or I shall reserve for him a piece of hell fire".²¹

The hadith, therefore, among other guiding principles, declared that the matters of evidence and proof belong to human affairs (*umur dunyawī*), consequently, its simplicity or complexity (or sophistication) progressively depends on human advancement in the field of technical knowledge to administer justice.

The Prophet (SAW) in order to guide his *ummah* (followers) practically on matters of forensic proofs, determined the paternity of Usamah bn Zaid based on the opinion of an expert on lineage, who depended for his analysis solely on a comparison between resembling bodily features, (as that was the human technical knowledge) in the field.²²

According to another report, the Prophet (SAW) relied on trace evidence for determining the victorious assassin of Abu Jahl, for sons of "Ufra" claimed that they together killed Abu Jahl. The prophet (SAW) asked them whether they have cleansed their swords, they said "no" when he looked at their swords, and found that, there was a blood still staining one of the swords. He decided that the owner of the stained sword was the rightful claimant, and Abu Jahl coat of mail (*salb*) was given to him²³

There is also another report that the Prophet (SAW) ruled the paternity of a boy on the basis of bedding (*firash*).²⁴ He is reported to have ordered a woman to be flogged on finding her pregnant while still unmarried.²⁵

Accordingly, the Prophet (SAW) by the foregoing decisions has established undeniable precedents to serve as instructive *stare decisis* for his followers regarding the leading matters of interest to the forensic sciences long before they even came into existence.

The companions of the Prophet (SAW), following his excellent examples, accorded clear recognition to what the whole of the forensic sciences and their analysis stand for in our time, for instance, caliph *Umar* convicted a person on the basis of odor of wine being emitted from his mouth²⁶ (today the breathalyzer can detect this).

²¹ Bn Umar, A, *Al-Dar Qutni, Sunnin Al Daral Qutni*; Daral Mahasin, Cairo, 1966, Vol. 4, p. 239.

²² Sahih *Bukhari*, Vol 3, No. 2341.

²³ Abubakar, A, *Sunnin Al-Kubura*, Daral Fikr, Beirut Vol. 6. (2000). p.305.

²⁴ Sunan Daral Qutni Vol. 4 p.241.

²⁵ *Ibid.* p. 251.

²⁶ Malik, A, *Al-Muwatta*, Turath Al Islamiyya Beirut, (1987) p. 242.

Most insightful is *Umar's* inaugurating admission of Caliph Ali's clever finding, through a process resembling today's forensic analysis, in a case whose facts are narrated as follows:

“During the reign of Umar, there was a woman who was strongly fond of a man, and attempted in various ways to seduce him, but all failed. Then she tried to implicate him by accusing him of committing fornication with her (molesting her). She took an egg and poured its yolk between her thighs and upon her cloth; thereafter she went to Umar and lodged a complaint that she was raped. Umar, on seeing her egg stained cloth, sought the opinion of a woman, who testified it to be semen, then he consulted Caliph Ali, to ascertain whether it was a semen as alleged by the woman. He soaked the traces of stains in boiled water and subsequently turned into white-solid. On smelling it, he found it to be egg – white not semen”²⁷

It is believed that the above decision alone can serve as a clear precedent in providing us with an undisputed legal framework to modernize our judicial system by incorporating the forensic sciences into the system to implement justice in the current environment of complex criminality and civil rights infringements.

The succeeding generations of jurists have also ruled on issue of great significance in the field of forensic evidence, under the heading of expert opinion (*ra'ay al-khabir*). The word *ra'ay* means opinion and *al-khabir* derived from the root word *khibr*, which means experienced, skilled, acquainted with and expert.²⁸ For instance, to decide on the virginity or otherwise of a woman, they required a wet nurse's opinion; to determine the amount of compensation for injuries, they sought opinions from the doctors, to allow the return of consumer goods on account of latent defects, they sought the help of specialist to prove it,²⁹ to mention but a few. Based on their *ijtihad*, expert opinion, aside from the *sunnah* and the practice of the companions, derives its validity from the *Quran* about Prophet Yusuf.³⁰

²⁷ Anwar, M.. *Al-Qara'in wa Dawruha fi-al-fiqh al-Jina'i Al-Islam*, Daral- Thaqafah, Al-Arabiyya, Cairo (1985) p.196.

²⁸ Muhammad, M. *Lisan Al-Arab*, Dar Sadir Lebanon, Vol. 4, pp. 226 – 227.

²⁹ -Zuhayli, M.. *Al-ithbat Fil Shara'ah Al-Islamiyya*, Dar Al-Maktabi, Damascus (1998)pp.142 – 145.

³⁰ Ibid.

In the Quran, reading about the incident of Prophet Yusuf's³¹ struggle to escape, and the resultant tearing of his shirt from the back, and the opinion of an expert (*wa shahida shahidun min ahliha*) and bore testimony a person from among her kinsfolk that it was a signing of truthfulness of Yusuf's claim, is held to constitute an authority in favor of admissibility of the opinion of a skilled person, as in forensic evidence. In this incidence the person in question was of great insight in knowing the occurrence of the incident of that description, and in that manner had the pre-modern skill of forensic sociologist or anthropologist of today.

Modern day forensic evidence has a strong basis in Islamic law, as it was validated on the basis of basic source of legitimacy and legality i.e. Quran, *sunnah* and Islamic law scholars in Islamic paradigm. The need for its contemporary use is a question of applying justice in a modern condition, in the process of which a traditional approach would lead to a collapse. This necessity has already been felt in some Muslim jurisdictions, like Pakistan where forensic evidence is admissible in Shariah courts.

5.0 EVIDENTIAL WEIGHT ATTACHED TO FORENSIC EVIDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

Most of the authorities especially contemporary legal scholars, treat forensic evidence as a form of *qarinah* (circumstantial evidence) and articulate its evidentiary value according to the rule that govern *qarinah*. For example, the view has been expressed thus:

*As a matter of fact, on our contemporary time, there have emerged a number of powerful and clear forms of circumstantial evidence and indicators in the field of proof and evidence. For example, the identification of culprit through fingerprints, blood testing, photographs, sound recordings and blood sampling... but the court has to be extremely cautious in using them, as the chances of tampering with them are greatly worrisome.*³²

Another contemporary scholar classifies a number of forensic processes as circumstantial evidence, these includes: the result of an autopsy on the dead body, identification by tracks, footprints, finger impressions, handwriting, blood stains, marks of injuries, marks of violence about the genitals on the body of a rape victim (*zina bi al-jabr*)

³¹ Q 12: 2 – 7.

³² Al Zuhayhli, op cit, p. 61.

and possession of incriminating objects, such as the weapon of the offence, and other trace evidences, such as, tyre and radiator marks on the victim's body and clothing in a case of hit and ran accident³³

It was also opined that terming forensic evidence as *al-qara'in al-muhaddatha* (the modern forms of circumstantial evidence). to conduct an autopsy to determine the cause of death (especially when the culprit after strangling the deceased, has hanged victim in order to make it appear as if he has committed suicide): to conduct blood tests for the purpose of identification; to verify the footprints and finger impressions found on the object used in the killing and comparing it with that of the indicted person, are all tools which ascertain the authenticity and reliability of evidence available before the court and are admissible in Islam.³⁴

However, it seems that greater weight is assigned to some forms of forensic tests on identification, such as finger impressions, but still as a *qarinah qat'ah* (very strong/conclusive type of circumstantial evidence). Forensic Science established that no finger impressions of two individuals are identical a fact stated in the Quran, that one's feet and hands depose evidence against him in the hereafter and this is confirmed today by Science.³⁵

A critical examination of the line of arguments presented above, however, points to the influence of the traditional approach to evidence and proof that has greatly shaped the thinking of our jurists, in their attempt to articulate a legal position regarding the evidentiary weight of forensic evidence in Islamic jurisprudence. In Islamic jurisprudence, judges are divided on this issue. According to the majority³⁶ once a piece of evidence is classified as *qarinah*, then its evidential weight is seriously doubted, thus in terms of quality, it is incapable of proving or disproving serious crimes called *hudud and qisas*. Their main arguments are:

1. The general rule is that a case has to be proved by direct evidence, such as oral testimony (*shahadah*), confession (*al-iqrar*), and oath (*yamin*). In the absence of

³³ Anwarullah, A, *Principles of Evidence in Islam*, A.S Noordeen Press, Kuwala Lampur, Malaysia, (1999) pp. 113 - 118

³⁴ Dabur, M, *Al-Qara'in wa Dauruha Fi Al-Fiqh Al-Jina'i Al-Islami*, Thaqafah Al-Arabiyya, Cairo (1985) p.201.

³⁵ Q 36:65.

³⁶ Ibn Ma'juz M, *Wasa'il Al-Ithbat Fi Al-fiqh Al-Islam*, Dar Al-Baida, Beirut, (1984). pp 13 - 14.

these, the court can use other indirect evidence such as *qara'in* to make inference from them about the truth of the matter contested before it.³⁷

2. In terms of evidentiary weight, indications and signs (*amarat/qara'in*) do not yield positive knowledge in order to convince the court as to the commission of fixed crimes (*hudud and qisas*), no matter how strong a *qarinah* may be, it still rest on probability and is tainted with doubt and obscurity, thus *hudud* and *qisas*, being punishment nullified with doubts cannot be established by *qara'in*.³⁸

To substantiate this view, they cite an incidence that happened in the time of Caliph Ali as follows:

*In the case a butcher, holding a sword was found standing by, beside a murdered person still bleeding, and was caught and brought before the caliph. In the circumstances, it was strongly believed that, he must have been the killer, but when he was handed to the executioner to be executed, the real culprit appeared and confessed that, it was he who has done that, upon the inquiry from the butcher as to why he did not deny that he was not the killer; he replied: " the situation that I was arrested by your men my sword stained with blood, and standing by the slain, and people remark by telling that no one killed the deceased except him, made me certain that you would not believe my defense in the circumstances so I confessed submitting my case to Allah (SWT)."*³⁹

It may be contended, however, that were this type of case to happen today and judges with the advantage of scientific evidence within their reach could safely determine the real culprit. This case simply requires investigation of the butcher's specimen of the blood stained knife by which not only the butcher would be exculpated from the accusation under the circumstance, the true identity of the real offender would be uncovered. A minority of the scholars, on the other hand, regard *qarinah* as sufficient evidence, like the testimony of

³⁷ Zuhaili, p cit, p. 69.

³⁸ Bek, A, *Turuk Al-Ithbat Al- Shar'iyya.. Wasil Ala – uddeni*, Azhar Cairo, (1985) p. 450.

³⁹ Ibn Qayyam, A, *Al-Turuk Al-Hukmiyya Thaqafah*, Al-Arabiyya, Cairo 2001, p. 46.

witness, or his confession. This is mainly because of their extended definition of evidence in Islamic law. For instance, *Ibn Qayyim* maintains:

Evidence, (al-hujjiyya) as an umbrella term, stands for all that manifest the truth and disclose it, anyone who restricts it to two eye-witnesses or four of them or one of such witnesses does not do justice to the true signification of the term. The Holy Quran never uses the word bayyinah to mean two witnesses alone. The Qur'anic connotations of the word bayyinah, therefore, are; hujja (proof), dalil (evidence) and burham (clear proof)⁴⁰

This understanding is agreed upon by contemporary thinkers such as Ata al-Sid when he maintains:

The mufasssirun are unanimous in their understanding of bayyinah to mean the establishment of proof, either mental such as, clear argument, or material evidence or both. In the legal sense the word, "bayyinah" is an umbrella term applied simultaneously to a number of methods of proof such as confession (iqrar), testimony (shahadah) and circumstantial evidence (qarinah).⁴¹

Regarding *qarinah*, it is specifically observed thus:

Qaria'in is of three categories in terms of their weight and strength of evidential values: the strong should be relied upon, the weak that should be rejected and the medium which should be verified and caution should be exercised in using them.⁴²

Accordingly, forensic evidence of today represents the strong (conclusive) *qarinah* that *Ibn Qayyim* was envisaging. It is also contended as to the conclusiveness of *qarinah* and argued as follows:

From among the methods upon which the judge based his decisions, are the circumstances (indications) which show the existence of what is required to become known by such decisions. Decision upon such indications, which are

⁴⁰ Ibn Qayyam, Op cit, p. 64.

⁴¹ Ata.Alsid, H. .*The Hudud*, Thaqafah, Al-Arabiyya,Cairo , (1998) p.158

⁴² Al-Bahuti, Y, *Kashshaf Al- Qina ala Matn Al-Iqud*, Dar-alFikr, Beirut , Vol. 6. (1982) p.. 431.

so clear that they amount to conclusive report (evidence), is valid, for example, in a situation where a person comes out of a house, wielding a knife and his cloth stained with blood, moving fast with symptoms of fear, on seeing this, people enter into the house and found a man has been stabbed and there is no any other person except the one who went out of the house. This is sufficient that the escaping man was the assailant. No attention is paid on mere supposition (al-ihimal) that someone else has killed the man and jumped over the wall or he himself has committed suicide. As such presumption can only be rebutted if there is a clear proof against it, but not the mere chance which is too remote.⁴³

The above example of the erudite jurist is very revealing, for, if such happens in reality, surely, it would be resolved on the basis of *qarinah*, a doctrine that emanated from *qarinah* itself.

In a nutshell, the reality about forensic evidence sufficiently supports the view of its admissibility as a strong *qarinah*, as pointed out by some leading classical jurists like Ibn Qayyim. The argument of doubt as a nullifying principle of the punishment for serious offences, raised by the majority can be overcome by the cumulative force of other supporting circumstances that are consistent with the findings by the forensic experts.⁴⁴

6.0 FORENSIC EXPERT OPINION

Opinion of expert is one of the sources of proof of crime or a claim under Islamic law. Expert's evidence is the testimony which is given in relation to some scientific, technical or professional matter by experts. i.e. a person qualified to speak authoritatively by reason of their special training, skill or familiarity with the subject. It assists the court to determine the facts in issue.⁴⁵

The opinion of expert has been given great importance in Islamic law where the Glorious Quran provided:

⁴³libn Abidin, M, *Majma'at Risalat ibn Abidin*, Sahayl Academy Press, Lahore, (1976) p. 128,

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

“And before you also the apostles we sent were but men to whom we granted inspiration. If you do not realize this, ask those who have knowledge.”⁴⁶

Expert opinion was also accorded recognition as evidence from the *Sunnah* of Prophet (PBUH). It has been related in *Muwatta* of *Imam Malik* on the authority of *Abdullahi bn Abubakar* who relates it from his father who said: that, a thief stole some fruits during the period of Caliph *Usman Bn Affan (RA)*. *The Caliph* ordered that, its value should be fixed by expert.⁴⁷

Furthermore, there is another classification by *Ibn Asim in Tuhfah*, of Islamic evidence where scholars categorized evidence based on the number of witnesses.⁴⁸ Viz:

1. Evidence in incidence of *Zina* i.e. (adultery or fornication). In this respect, four reliable male witnesses are required who saw the actual commission of the act of *Zina*. Less than four (4) witnesses are not enough to testify and secure a conviction in the offence of adultery. “Provide four witnesses among you to give evidence against them (the adulterers).⁴⁹

2. Incident other than *Zina*. In this circumstance two reliable witnesses are enough to testify.⁵⁰

3. Evidence of Monetary transaction, in which two reliable male witnesses or one male and two females are required.⁵¹ “. . . and call in two witness of two from among your men, two witnesses, but if there are no two men, then a man and two women.⁵²

4. Evidence of Pregnancy and Menstruation and anything which can only be perceived by females. In such cases two female witnesses are sufficient.⁵³

5. Evidence in cases other than *hudud*, i.e. cases that involve the rights of individual alone i.e. between individuals. One male witness and the oath of the claimant is enough,⁵⁴ by

⁴⁶ Q 16:43

⁴⁷ Malik, *Muwatta Malik*, Darul fikr, Turkey 2000, p.754

⁴⁸ Ibn Asim, M, op cit, p, 7.

⁴⁹ Surah Al Nisai, Q4 :15.

⁵⁰ Ibn Asim, M, opcit,

⁵¹ Surah Baqara, Q2:282.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵⁴ Ibn Asim, M, op cit, P.14

virtue of the prophetic tradition reported by *Abdullahi bn Abbas*(RA) Said: “Prophet (S.A.W) gave judgment relying upon the evidence of one witness and the oath of the claimant.”⁵⁵

Besides, there are quite a number of prophetic traditions which recognize expert opinion or evidence involving questions of techniques.

6.1 ROLE OF FORENSIC EXPERT IN DETERMINING THE ADMISSIBILITY OR OTHERWISE OF FORENSIC EVIDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

The role of a forensic expert is very crucial in determining the question of admissibility of forensic evidence, this is because dealing with intangible electronic data during the various stages of judicial proceedings,⁵⁶ requires more than merely having a working knowledge of the computer which lawyers and prosecutors may possess, it is the expert who undertakes the following tasks:⁵⁷ to identify the potential source of electronic data in the party’s computer system in a law suit; develop strategic plan for the acquisition of the electronic data on the party’s computer system; anticipate as to how to respond to the objections made by the other opposing party; suggest a cost-effective means of discovering the electronic data; retrieve hidden electronic data from other party’s device; provide special software to preserve forensic evidence, determine the accuracy and authenticity of forensic evidence, educate the lawyers and the courts about the technical aspect of the technology, break passwords in order to access certain types of data and avoid the removal of innocent material from the device.

Consequently, with the aid of the revolution in the field of information technology, the monitoring flood of computer related lawsuits and criminal prosecutions, which require all the above, the administration of justice cannot operate without the aid of experts in the field.

7.0 CONCLUSION

On the basis of the above, one can understand that forensic evidence as is a scientific method of investigation and submit that, it can help immensely in the administration of justice, in determining the cause of death by post mortem or ascertaining facts, forensic

⁵⁵ Sahih Muslim pp 215

⁵⁶USA Federal Rules of Evidence, op cit, p. 66.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

evidence gets recognition and become admissible under Islamic law as a mode of proof after being corroborated. Under Islamic law principle of "*Ra'ay al-Khabir*" it has been shown that, Islamic law sources contain enough basis for its accommodation either as *qarinah* (circumstantial evidence) or as *ra'ay al- khabir* (expert opinion). Islamic law has validated scientific proofs for practical purposes and using a degree of caution in so doing, is used in conjunction with other corroborative evidence based on the broad definition of "*bayyinah*" as articulated by some great legal scholars like *Ibn Qayyim Al-Jawzey*. It is therefore reveals that forensic evidence may be admitted provided its reliability and authenticity is established. And it is also recommending that, our Islamic law scholars and judges of *Shariah* Courts shall strive and learnt Information and Communication Technology to properly apply the Islamic Law.